

INTERACTIVE METHODS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13881184>

Abstract. *The article examines interactive methods aimed at the development of foreign language communicative competence of university students. Special attention is paid to the use of role-playing games, simulations and project-based learning in the educational process. The effectiveness of these methods in the context of improving communication skills in a foreign language is analyzed, as well as their impact on student motivation and interaction in the learning environment.*

Keywords: *communicative competence, interactive methods, role play, project method, information technologies.*

Introduction. Communicative competence is fundamental to a successful life in modern society, as it is of great importance for all spheres of life. Therefore, it is not surprising that communicative competence is the subject of many theoretical and empirical approaches and, consequently, research on this topic is diverse.

Communicative competence is the ability and willingness of a person to engage in communication or carry out communication, and foreign language communicative competence (FLCC) is the ability to communicate in a foreign language, understand foreign language speech, and correctly express their thoughts and opinions in another language.

The process of development of FLCC is continuous, this competence does not end with the graduation of students from universities, but on the contrary accompanies them in their further professional activities as a specialist and contributes to career growth.

Currently, changes are being made to the content of education, approaches and methods are changing and more modern and effective ones are being introduced, such as competence-based, communicative and competence-oriented, which help students to feel the real communicative environment and develop practical knowledge of a foreign language. These approaches include interactive methods such as the project method, role-playing games, case method, simulations, debates, discussions, the use of various Internet resources, etc.

Role-plays

Role-playing games allow students to practice language in simulated situations, which contributes to the development of communication skills and adaptation to various communicative contexts. In such games, students take on different roles and interact with each other, which help them apply the learned language structures in real situations [8]. Research shows that role-playing games help to increase students' confidence in using a foreign language and improve their ability to communicate spontaneously [6].

Simulations

Simulations, such as simulating business negotiations or customer service, create realistic scenarios in which students can apply language in professional contexts. Such methods help

students to master specialized vocabulary and develop problem-solving skills [3]. Simulations also helps to take into account cultural characteristics and specific requirements of various fields, which makes learning more focused and effective.

Project method

The project method has been used in teaching foreign languages for a long time. At first, it was called the problem method, and its essence was for students to find a solution to the problem on their own. Over time, this method has evolved, but the essence remains the same – through active and independent activity to find a solution to one or more problems and acquire knowledge, as well as apply this knowledge in practice [3].

The project method, according to many researchers, is considered one of the most effective methods of organizing the educational process, based on the principles of personality-oriented education, and represents an active independent creative activity of students to solve problems.

Project-based learning involves completing complex tasks that require the use of language to create products, such as presentations, reports, or research. This method helps to integrate language skills with critical thinking and teamwork. In project-based learning, students actively use language to achieve specific goals, which contributes to a deeper assimilation of vocabulary and grammar [4]. Lexical and grammatical skills are also an integral part in the development of communicative competence [1]. Projects can include both individual and group assignments, which contributes to the development of skills of cooperation and collective discussion.

The use of interactive methods in the learning process

Interactive teaching methods used in the process of teaching English at a non-linguistic university are aimed at enhancing the educational and cognitive activities of students, increasing their interest and motivation to learn a foreign language, and therefore improving the quality of education. All of the above methods are often used in English classes. However, in this paper we preferred to describe the process of applying the project method in self-study among first-year students of Nukus branch of Tashkent university of information technologies. An example of this method is the creation of a university magazine, which is published once a month and should contain university news, interviews with students or teachers, useful tips, an entertainment section, etc. This project is aimed at achieving several key goals. Firstly, it promotes the development of language skills, which includes improving reading, writing and speaking skills. Secondly, this assignment helps to develop teamwork skills by teaching students how to collaborate and solve problems together. And, thirdly, the project deepens knowledge in the field of information technology and about the university.

Before starting work, students are divided into groups of 4-5 people, including choosing a captain who will coordinate the work process and represent the group. Each team discusses and defines the structure of the journal and its sections. After completing the initial stage, students begin collecting information on each section, which includes researching or searching for the latest university events, preparing questions and conducting interviews, developing crosswords and other entertainment materials, as well as discussing the collected information and its further use. In the next stage, students assign roles, i.e. some write texts, others design the magazine. However, everyone participates in the editing of materials, as it contributes to the development of writing and text skills. After completing the work on the journal, each team presents its project to the rest of the students. The presentation includes a description of the information collection process, writing and editing methods, as well as knowledge and skills acquired during the work. At the

final stage, students listen to the opinions of the teacher and classmates, which allows them to analyze the results of their work and identify opportunities for further development.

An independent task of this kind has been used more than once among students. Not only the work on the creation of the university magazine, but also other project tasks contribute to the development of language skills and the formation of the necessary competencies for successful study at the university.

By applying various tasks of the interactive method in teaching English, we believe that students increase their desire and motivation to learn a foreign language [5] and develop communicative competence, which is so important in today's world. Research shows that the use of role-playing games and simulations helps students develop communication skills and confidence in language [7].

Conclusion. Interactive methods such as role-playing games, simulations and project-based learning play a key role in the development of foreign language communicative competence of university students. These methods ensure the practical application of language in various contexts, contribute to the improvement of communication skills and increase the motivation of students. To achieve the best results, it is important to integrate interactive methods into existing curricula and programs, adapting them to specific learning needs and goals.

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